

A one-pot route to the synthesis of functionalized butan-1-one analogues

A. R. Naresh Raj and C. A. M. A. Huq*

P.G. and Research Department of Chemistry, The New College (Affiliated to the University of Madras),
Chennai-600 014, India

E-mail : drmdabdulhuq@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 22 July 2008, accepted 19 December 2008

Abstract : We report the first instance where the treatment of 1-*N*-phenyl-2-pyrrolidinone with RMgX gave acyclic nitrogen based compounds i.e. 1-aryl-4-(arylamino)butan-1-one derivatives instead of fused nitrogen heterocycles. The formation of 1-aryl-4-(arylamino)butan-1-one derivatives involves unusual ring opening.

Keywords : 1-*N*-Phenyl-2-pyrrolidinone, ring opening reaction, Grignard reaction.

Introduction

New strategies for the synthesis of fused ring (tricyclic or polycyclic) system have gained considerable prominence in recent years owing to the existence of these frame works in many naturally occurring compounds¹. In continuation of our current interest in the synthesis of tricyclic and polycyclic compounds²⁻⁷, we have made an attempt to synthesize tetracyclic compounds through an aromatic 3-aza-Cope rearrangement⁸⁻¹⁰. To accomplish the tetracyclic compounds, initially we made an attempt

to synthesise a tertiary alcohol which serves as a precursor for the synthesis of polycyclic compounds. But latter we have found that, the tertiary alcohol was highly unstable and undergo ring opening to give 1-aryl-4-(arylamino)butan-1-one analogues 3(a-e).

Results and discussion

The 1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)butan-1-one 3a was synthesized by the addition of 3 equiv. of phenylmagnesium bromide to 1-*N*-phenyl-2-pyrrolidinone in dry THF (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The reaction proceeds through nucleophilic addition of phenylmagnesium bromide to the ketone **1**. The unstable intermediate formed, undergoes ring opening instead of undergoing [3,3] sigmatropic rearrangement which we have expected. The general mechanism of the formation of the observed products **3(a-e)** and expected products **4(a-e)** are indicated in Scheme 2 and Scheme 3 respectively.

bs). The aromatic protons gave signals at δ 6.56–7.92 (10H, m). The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the compound **3a** showed peaks at δ 23.7, 35.9 and 43.3 for the methylene carbons. The aromatic carbons resonated at δ 113.0 to 148.2. The carbonyl carbon showed peak at δ 199.7 while for the 1-*N*-phenyl-2-pyrrolidinone **1**, which is the starting material, the carbonyl carbon peak was observed at δ 174.1. The mass spectrum of **3a** showed a peak at m/z 239 (M^+).

Scheme 2. General mechanism of the formation of the observed products **3(a-e)**.

Scheme 3. General mechanism of the formation of the expected product **4(a-e)**.

The compound **3a** was obtained as a pale yellow solid in 62% yield, m.p. 75–80 °C. The IR spectrum showed a strong peak at 1678.0 and 3379.1 cm^{-1} for the carbonyl CO and NH stretching respectively. The ^1H NMR of **3a** showed a signal at δ 1.98–2.02 (2H, m) for the methylene protons. The methylene protons adjacent to the carbonyl carbon and to the hetero atom gave a signal at δ 3.02 (2H, t, J 6.3 Hz) and at δ 3.15 (2H, t, J 6.3 Hz) respectively. The NH proton gave signal at δ 3.68 (1H,

The compound **3c** was obtained as a fluffy light brown solid in 72% yield, m.p. 70–75 °C. The IR spectrum showed strong peaks at 1666.4 and 3398.3 cm^{-1} for the CO and NH stretching respectively. The ^1H NMR of **3c** showed a signal at δ 1.84–1.89 (2H, m) for the methylene protons. The methyl protons gave signal at δ 2.22 (3H, s). The methylene protons adjacent to the carbonyl carbon and to the hetero atom gave a signal at δ 2.86 (2H, t, J 6.2 Hz) and at δ 3.01 (2H, t, J 6.2 Hz) respectively. The NH proton

Note

gave signal at δ 3.67 (1H, bs). The aromatic protons gave signals at δ 6.44–7.70 (9H, m). The ^{13}C NMR of **3c** showed a peak at δ 21.7 for the methyl carbon and showed peaks at δ 24.0, 36.0 and 43.5 respectively for the methylene carbons. The aromatic carbons resonated at δ 112.8 to 148.4. The carbonyl carbon showed peak at δ 199.6. The mass spectrum of **3c** showed a peak at m/z 253 (M^+). Identical results were obtained for other products. All the products exhibited satisfactory elemental analysis. Finally the products was further confirmed by single crystal X-ray analysis of **3a** (Fig. 1).

Elemental analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 2400B instrument. The starting materials **1** and **2a-e**, magnesium turnings were purchased (Aldrich) and used as received.

Representative procedure for the synthesis of 1-aryl-4-(arylamino)butane-1-one's **3a** :

To a solution of phenylmagnesium bromide in dry THF at 0 °C under N_2 atm. [prepared from Mg (0.9 g, 0.0375 mol) and bromobenzene **2a** (5.88 g, 3.95 ml, 0.0375 mol)], 1-*N*-phenyl-2-pyrrolidinone **1** (2.0 g, 0.0125

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of compound **3a**.

The reaction time and yield of the products **3(a-e)** are given in Table 1.

Entry	Product	R	R ¹	Stirring		Yield (%)
				0 °C (h)	RT (h)	
1	3a	H	H	2	3–5	62
2	b	CH ₃	H	2	3–5	68
3	c	H	CH ₃	2	3–5	72
4	d	OCH ₃	H	2	3–5	76
5	e	H	OCH ₃	2	3–5	80
6	f	–	–	2	3–5	60

RT = Room temperature.

Experimental

General :

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu FT-IR 8300 instrument. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol DX 303 HF spectrometer with Maspec system (msw/9629). ^1H and ^{13}C NMR were recorded in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard on a Bruker spectrometer at 300 and 75 MHz, respectively.

mol) in dry THF was added dropwise. After the addition the mixture was stirred at 0 °C under N_2 atm. for 2 h, then it was stirred at room temperature under N_2 atm. for 3–5 h. After the completion of reaction as evident from TLC, the reaction was quenched with a saturated solution of NH_4Cl (50 ml). The product was extracted into diethyl ether (2 × 50 ml). The ether layer was washed with water followed by brine and dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 and finally evaporated. Purification of the residue by column chromatography on silica gel (100–200 mesh) using hexane : ethyl acetate (9.5 : 0.5) as eluent affords **3a**.

Physical properties and spectroscopic details for the compounds **3a-e** :

1-Phenyl-4-(phenylamino)butan-1-one (**3a**) : Pale yellow solid (62%), m.p. 75–80 °C (Found : C, 80.12; H, 7.26; N, 5.93. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ requires : C, 80.30; H, 7.15; N, 5.85%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1678.0 (CO), 3379.1 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) δ 1.98–2.02 (2H, m), 3.01 (2H, t, J 6.2 Hz), 3.15 (2H, t, J 6.3 Hz), 3.68 (1H, bs, NH), 6.56–7.92 (10H, m, ArH); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) δ 23.7, 35.9, 43.3, 113.0, 117.1, 127.9, 128.1, 128.3, 128.5, 128.8, 129.1, 129.5, 132.9, 136.8, 148.2 and 199.7; m/z 239 (M^+).

1-(o-Tolyl)-4-(phenylamino)butan-1-one (3b) : Chocolate brown solid (68%), m.p. 82–83 °C (Found : C, 80.42; H, 7.63; N, 5.62. C₁₇H₁₉NO requires : C, 80.59; H, 7.55; N, 5.52%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1670.3 (CO), 3382.1 (NH) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) δ 1.86 (2H, m), 2.20 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.84 (2H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 3.00 (2H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 3.68 (1H, bs, NH), 6.42–7.68 (9H, m, ArH); δ_{C} (CDCl₃) δ 21.6, 24.0, 36.2, 43.4, 112.8, 117.2, 128.3, 129.3, 129.4, 134.4, 140.8, 148.5 and 199.58; *m/z* 253 (M⁺).

1-(p-Tolyl)-4-(phenylamino)butan-1-one (3c) : Fluffy light brown solid (72%), m.p. 70–75 °C (Found : C, 80.68; H, 7.44; N, 5.61. C₁₆H₁₇NO requires : C, 80.59; H, 7.55; N, 5.52%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1666.4 (CO), 3398.3 (NH) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) δ 1.84–1.89 (2H, m), 2.23 (3H, s), 2.86 (2H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 3.01 (2H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 3.67 (1H, bs, NH), 6.44–7.70 (9H, m); δ_{C} (CDCl₃) δ 21.7, 24.0, 36.0, 43.5, 112.8, 117.2, 128.2, 129.3, 129.4, 134.5, 143.9, 148.4 and 199.6; *m/z* 253 (M⁺).

1-(o-Anisyl)-4-(phenylamino)butan-1-one (3d) : Dark brown solid (76%), m.p. 48–50 °C (Found : C, 75.66; H, 7.21; N, 5.28. C₁₇H₁₉NO requires : C, 75.80; H, 7.10; N, 5.20%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1652.3 (CO), 3340.1 (NH) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) δ 1.86–1.98 (2H, m), 2.98 (2H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 3.07 (2H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 3.68 (1H, bs, NH), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.48–7.60 (9H, m, ArH); δ_{C} (CDCl₃) δ 24.0, 32.6, 43.4, 55.5, 111.6, 112.5, 116.7, 120.1, 120.5, 129.0, 139.4, 158.4 and 199.5; *m/z* 269 (M⁺).

1-(p-Anisyl)-4-(phenylamino)butan-1-one (3e) : Pale yellow solid (80%), m.p. 63–64 °C (Found : C, 75.93; H, 6.99; N, 5.34. C₁₇H₁₉NO requires : C, 75.80; H, 7.10; N, 5.20%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1643.2 (CO), 3336.6 (NH) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) δ 1.88–1.96 (2H, m), 2.96 (2H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 3.08 (2H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 3.62 (1H, bs, NH), 3.76 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.52–7.62 (9H, m, ArH); δ_{C} (CDCl₃) δ 24.0, 32.4, 43.4, 55.4, 111.6, 112.4, 116.7, 120.1, 120.5, 129.0, 139.3, 158.4 and 199.5; *m/z* 269 (M⁺).

1-Naphthyl-4-(phenylamino)butan-1-one (3f) : Light brown solid (60%), m.p. 90–92 °C (Found : C, 83.18; H, 6.45; N, 4.97. C₁₇H₁₉NO requires : C, 83.01; H, 6.61; N, 4.84%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1674.1 (CO), 3419.6 (NH) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) δ 1.90–1.96 (2H, m), 3.04 (2H, t), 3.20 (2H, t), 3.64 (1H, bs, NH), 6.46–8.72 (12H, m, ArH); δ_{C} (CDCl₃) δ 23.8, 36.2, 44.5, 113.2, 117.0, 126.2, 126.6, 128.3, 128.5, 129.6, 130.1, 133.1, 133.8 and 200.6; *m/z* 289 (M⁺).

In conclusion, our work reports a first instance where we have shown an easy route to the synthesis of butan-1-one analogues in a single step.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank SAIF, IIT, Chennai, for spectral data and the management of the New College, Chennai for providing us the necessary facilities.

References

- (a) L. A. Paquette and A. M. Doherty, in "Polyquinone Chemistry, Reactivity and Structural Concepts Organic Chemistry", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1989, Vol. 26; (b) O. Sticher, in "New Natural Products and Plant Drugs with Pharmacological, Biology or Therapeutic Activity", eds. G. Wagner and P. Wolff, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1977; (c) C. H. Heath Cock, in "Synthesis of Natural Products", ed. T. Apsimon, Wiley, New York, 1973. Vols. 2 and 5; (d) L. Porter, *Chem. Rev.*, 1967, **67**, 441; (e) T. Hudlicky, T. T. Kutchan, S. R. Wilson and D. T. Mao, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 6351.
- P. Geetha, C. A. M. A. Huq, K. Rajagopalan and S. Swaminathan, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, **23**, 569.
- A. K. Rahiman, S. S. Hussaini and C. A. M. A. Huq, *Curr. Sci.*, 2002, **82**, 1138.
- S. S. Hussaini, V. Sriraman and C. A. M. A. Huq, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 249.
- A. Rasheeth and C. A. M. A. Huq, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, **37**, 1557.
- S. S. Hussaini, A. R. Naresh Raj and C. A. M. A. Huq, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 775.
- S. S. Hussaini and C. A. M. A. Huq, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 212.
- Base-promoted Aza-Cope rearrangement/Mannich reaction : (a) M. Kakimoto and M. Okawara, *Chem. Lett.*, 1979, 1171; (b) M. E. Okazaki, PhD Dissertation, University of California, Irvine, 1986; (c) W. G. Earley, J. E. Jacobsen, A. Madin, G. P. Meier, C. J. O'Donnell, T. Oh, D. W. Old, L. E. Overman and M. J. Sharp, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 18046.
- For Reviews that include a discussion of aromatic 3-aza-Cope rearrangement, see : (a) G. B. Bennett, *Synthesis*, 1977, 589; (b) H. Heimgartner, H. J. Hansen and H. Schmid, *Adv. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **9**, 655; (c) R. P. Lutz, *Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **84**, 205; (d) N. M. Przheval'skii and I. I. Grandberg, *Russ. Chem. Rev.*, 1987, **56**, 477.
- (a) L. G. Beholz and J. R. Stille, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 5095; (b) R. Sreekumar and R. Padmakumar, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 5281.